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MPPT Technique Based-on Microcontroller Using Combination of Perturb Observe and Constant Voltage Algorithm

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Abstract-Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) is supporting device for power harvesting on Solar Photovoltaic (PV) Power Generator. This system means to optimize power transfer from solar panel array to battery. Power transferring process shown in solar panel characteristic as I-V curve. This curve depends on weather condition, such as temperature and irradiation level of the sunlight. The purpose of this research is to design hardware of MPPT system based on Atmega16 microcontroller. This system implements combination of Constant Voltage and Perturb & Observe algorithms. To control the output voltage, fuzzy logic system is used to determine the value of PWM. The conclusions of this research are; first, devising switching PWM using prescaler of 1024, with clock of microcontroller on its default 1 MHz, and 50% duty cycle generated the highest efficiency of the system, that is 58.03%, on the other hand, it has the lowest inductor impedance value, that is 5.03 ohm. Second, MPPT hardware which has been devised has the average efficiency of 88.89%.

Keywords: weather condition, microcontroller.

Introduction

Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT)[1]–[3] is a support system for the power transfer process in the Solar Power Plant (PLTS) system. MPPT has a function to optimize the transfer of power from solar panels to batteries. This power transfer process is seen in the characteristics of solar panels on the V-I curve. This non-linear V-I curve depends on weather conditions[4], namely the temperature and the level of solar irradiation. Each curve has a point where the maximum power transfer takes place, i.e. the coordinates (V_{mpp} , I_{mpp}), this point is called the Maximum Power Point. The MPPT algorithm is used to track maximum power points. Then change the operational voltage to V_{mpp} voltage with a buck converter circuit using PWM switching mode.

The purpose of this research is to design and design MPPT system hardware based on Atmega16 microcontroller[5]–[9][10]. In this system, a Constant Voltage Tracking and Perturb & Observe algorithm is implemented. Control of system output voltage is used fuzzy logic[11]–[13][14]–[16] as a decision maker for PWM values. This PWM value determines the duty cycle of the buck converter circuit to reduce the solar panel input voltage to the V_{mpp} voltage.

Therefore, this study has formulated a problem that can be taken, namely how to design and design MPPT systems for solar panels.

The limitation of the problem in this study is the MPPT system which is designed for a 12/24 V PLTS system with a maximum current of 20 A based on the Atmega16 microcontroller[17]. Tracking algorithm using Constant Voltage and Perturb & Observe. And controlling the output voltage using fuzzy logic[18]–[20][21]–[23].

Methodology

The methodology used in conducting research is an experimental approach to the laboratory and testing of systems in the field. Broadly speaking the research conducted includes literature review, preparation of tools and materials, design, simulation, hardware assembly, programming, testing and then data analysis.

2.1 System work

This MPPT is used for PV systems with 12V voltage and maximum current of 20A. The PV specifications used for the basis of this study are explained in Table 1.

Table 1. PV GC Solar Model SUPS100 specification

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Value</i>
<i>Open circuit voltage</i>	Voc	23.67 V
<i>Short circuit current</i>	Isc	10 A
<i>Maximum voltage</i>	Vmpp	16.6 V
<i>Maximum current</i>	Impp	8 A
<i>Power</i>	P	100 Wp

In doing hardware design, what is done first is to make a system concept. The concept is made in the form of a block diagram that illustrates the components of the system and the relationships between these components.

Figure 1. System Block Diagram

Figure 1 is the result of MPPT system design. In MPPT there are 2 kinds of inputs for the control process, the first voltage sensor, used to get the voltage parameters of open circuit PV when switching at DC / DC is 0, the measurement voltage will be input to the Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) on the microcontroller[24] to be used reference (Voc) on subsequent tracking algorithm processing. The second voltage sensor is combined with a current sensor, the measured voltage and current parameters are used for the main algorithm, namely tracking the maximum power point (Maximum Power Point Tracking). The voltage at the maximum power point is then used as a reference voltage (Vref). Then the charging voltage is reduced to a reference voltage (Vref) by a buck converter circuit with an OCR1A PWM signal controlled by uC.

2.2 Hardware design

2.2.1 PWM interface

Variation or change in charging voltage is required for the tracking of maximum power points using the Perturb & Observe algorithm. In fact, the location of the maximum power point changes with changes in solar irradiation and PV temperature. The maximum power point[25]–[29] in question is the peak value on the PV power characteristic curve. To do this algorithm, scanning process from voltage $(0,76.V_{oc}) - 1V$ to $(0,76.V_{oc}) + 1V$ is needed. This scanning process is commonly called perturb, which varies the voltage so that each voltage variation has a current value. Continuing the process of observation, i.e. each variation of the voltage is multiplied by the current value so that the variation in the power value of the perturb process is seen. This voltage at the highest power value (Vmpp) is used as the reference voltage. Then this perturb process requires a

voltage converter circuit. The next voltage converter circuit is also used to convert the charging voltage into a reference voltage.

In this study, the voltage converter is controlled by a microcontroller[30] so an interface or interface between the microcontroller[9], [18], [20], [21], [31] and the PWM Switching Mode[32]–[34] circuit is needed.

Figure 2. Switching PWM schematic

2.2.2 Voltage sensor

The voltage sensor is designed for the 0-32V measurement range. The voltage sensor used is quite simple using only the principle of voltage dividers.

2.2.3 Current sensor

In designing the current sensor, the circuit used is also quite simple because it uses the ACS 712-20A current sensor. This sensor has a maximum limit of 20A measurement. While the measurement range is -20A to 20A. IP+ legs are connected on the positive side of the connection being measured and IP- on the negative side. The operating voltage of this sensor is 5 V, connected to the Vcc foot. A capacitor of 1uF is used for signal filtration, then connected to ground (GND). The VOUT foot is the output signal from this sensor which is connected to the ADC pin on the microcontroller[35].

2.2.4 Buck converter

The design of the buck converter is based on the MPPT design demands as follows:

- a. Vin Input Voltage : 20.02 Volt
- b. Vout Output Voltage : 12 Volts
- c. The average output DC current Io : 20A
- d. Fs switching frequency : 3.8 Hz (clock 1Mhz no prescaler)
- e. Minimum output current I1 : 0.1 x Io

These specifications are adjusted to the input voltage generated by the photovoltaic module with the voltage needed to charge the battery, while for other quantities adjusted to the availability of components in the market.

2.2.5 Microcontroller

Microcontroller[36]–[38] is the most important part of the system designed. This section has a function as a data processing center and implementing the main functions of the MPPT system algorithm. The choice of microcontroller[39] type is adjusted to the system requirements. Atmega16 was chosen because its features and specifications meet the needs of the MPPT system and controller.

Figure 3.ATMega 16 system minimum schematic

2.3 Firmware design

To do the work process of the device, the microcontroller must first be uploaded by the program. The programming process is carried out by making a program listing using compiler software or IDE, then compiling the program so that the program is obtained in the form of hexa language, and finally is downloading the program in hexa language to the microcontroller. To download, the Khazama AVR downloader downloader and downloader device are needed which connects the microcontroller to the computer via USB (Universal Serial Bus). The program listing was created using the AVRStudio4 compiler software in the C programming language. AVRStudio4 was chosen because this software is specifically for programming the AVR family of microcontrollers. Inside is a library that makes it easy to program the AVR microcontroller.

Broadly speaking, the program uploaded to the microcontroller functions to read the PLTS system parameters with the ADC, tracking the maximum power point, controlling the output voltage, and presenting the actual data display of the PLTS system. The general program flow can be displayed through the flow chart in Figure 4.

Figure 4. System work flow chart

The program is made with several sequential parts. The first part is the header section containing the library files included in the program, the second part is defining devices that define devices connected to the microcontroller, the third part is the definition of global variables used in the program, the fourth part is the definition of functions such as subroutines, and the last part is the main procedure carried out by the program.

This program is run to track the voltage V_{mpp} (Maximum Power Point), where at that voltage the power harvested from PV to the battery is maximum. This tracking step uses 2 tracking algorithms, namely constant voltage and perturb & observe.

The first step is the constant voltage algorithm to track the MPP voltage. V_{oc} value is obtained by reading the voltage when the PV and the battery are connected open (cut connection). This voltage is a property of the PV module which depends on temperature and irradiation level.

2.4 Control algorithm

Figure 5. Perturb Observe algorithm work flow chart

In the flow chart above, it is explained that the tracking direction is positive or goes up when the value of P [n] is more than P [i-1]. Conversely, if the value of P [i] is less than P [i-1], the system will take voltage data (PV Volt.[i-1]) as the MPP voltage.

2.5 Performance analysis

The results obtained from this research are MPPT controller hardware, software in the form of programs, and the results of field testing. The first analysis is to analyze the workings of the system and the workings of the components that make up the system. Then what is done next is to make a summary of the test results in tables and graphs. The test is carried out with a simulation using Proteus 7.7 software, electronic simulation on the project board, and then also measures the performance of the device when installed on a PLTS system. Testing is done in stages. All components are tested first starting from the measurement of voltage and current, the application of the MPPT algorithm, to the application of fuzzy control[40]–[42][43]–[45].

In general, testing is carried out to determine the efficiency of the device when it is installed on a solar power system in the field. The measurement is done by adding several lines in the program to calculate the efficiency of the device every 1 second. Measurements are also displayed on the LCD display. Device efficiency is calculated by the following formula:

$$= \frac{Vout * Iout}{Vin * Iin} \times 100\% = \frac{Pout}{Pin} \times 100\%$$

Result and Discussion

MPPT system testing is done by measuring the voltage and current input as well as the voltage and current output of the PV-VP system. Tests using Sharp 195 Wp brand solar panels and 100Ah Sigellum brand batteries. This test was carried out for 2 days, on Saturday 31 August 2013 and Sunday 1 September 2013. The test was carried out at the location in the yard of the UGM Center for Energy Studies located at Sekip Blok K1 A, UGM, Sleman Yogyakarta. The UGM PSE office is located at latitude 7 ° 46'17.80 "S and longitude 110 ° 22'30.82" T. This test is carried out for 2 days with each day divided into 3 testing periods, namely morning, afternoon and evening. The test data are input voltage and current, output voltage and current, and PWM value. The five parameters are displayed on the LCD display. Data is collected every 1 minute. In this test the MPPT device is mounted on a battery charging system with solar panels starting from the morning period test to the nonstop afternoon.

Figure 6.(a) Test result conducted on Saturday, (b) Test result conducted on Monday

Table 2.MPPT system test

<i>Test day</i>	<i>Day period</i>	<i>Average Power in (W)</i>	<i>Average Power out (W)</i>	<i>Average efficiency (%)</i>
<i>Saturday</i>	<i>Morning</i>	36.32	32.73	90.20
	<i>Noon</i>	35.41	31.05	88.16
	<i>Afternoon</i>	7.35	6.59	89.76
<i>Monday</i>	<i>Morning</i>	33.77	30.00	88.83
	<i>Noon</i>	40.85	35.90	88.03

<i>Afternoon</i>	30.57	26.84	88.42
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Table 2 shows that the average input and output power in the afternoon period is highest between morning and evening periods. That is because in the afternoon period the weather experiences significant up and down changes at the beginning and end of testing.

The overall MPPT system efficiency shows good system performance with a value of not less than 88%. Then to find out the performance of the PV-VP system using MPPT, two tests of the PV-VP system were tested in identical testing conditions. The test is done by comparing the power harvested in the PV-VP system with MPPT and without MPPT.

Table 3. System test with or without MPPT

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>System without MPPT</i>	<i>System with MPPT</i>
<i>Average voltage (V)</i>	12.39	12.91
<i>Average current (A)</i>	0.36	0.38
<i>Average power (P)</i>	4.40	4.90

Conclusion

The design of MPPT devices tested in the field using battery load, by implementing a combination of the Constant Voltage tracking algorithm and Perturb and Observe, and controlling voltage using the Fuzzy logic Tsukamoto method, produces an average system efficiency of 88.89%. Whereas in laboratory testing, the PLTS system with MPPT was able to increase the value of power transfer by 11.36% compared to the PLTS system without MPPT.

Suggestions for developing research on the implementation of the MPPT system for a Solar Power Plant system is using or varying the microcontroller clock frequency more than the default frequency for better system efficiency. It also uses other tracking algorithms, such as, Hill Climb Search, Incremental Conductance, PI, etc.

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